

D7.5: Clustering and Commercial Ecosystem

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Table of Contents

1	Introduction.....	10
1.1	ZeroW project summary aims, objectives and outputs in the context of the originating work package.....	10
1.2	Mapping ZeroW outputs.....	11
1.3	Vision, Objectives and Strategy.....	14
1.3.1	Objectives & Vision.....	14
1.3.2	Ecosystem set-up and member engagement strategy.....	18
2	Main Actions and Timelines	21
2.1	Main Actions	21
2.1.1	Main Actions (M3–M12)	22
2.1.2	Main Actions (M12–M19)	25
2.1.3	Main Actions (M19–M30)	28
2.1.4	Main Actions (M30–M48)	30
2.2	Timeline and Strategy	31
2.3	Deliverable & Milestone timeline and objective	36
2.4	Internal project set-up: partners’ roles.....	37
3	Synergies	39
3.1	Internal project set-up: partners’ roles.....	39
3.2	Internal Project Set-up: SILLS and Clusters Roles.....	40
3.3	External synergies: Sister Projects	45
3.4	Internal project set-up: AB members	47
3.3	Internal and External Groups and Platforms.....	48
3.5	Recruitment Campaign for the Ecosystem Expansion.....	50
4	Organisation & Implementation	51
4.1	ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem Structure	51
4.2	ZeroFLW Capacity Building Sessions for Engagement.....	53
4.3	Sustainability of the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem	55
5	Summary	56
6	References.....	58
7	Appendix I: List of entities enrolled to the ZeroW Business Ecosystem	59
8	Appendix II: Internal and External Questionnaires Results.....	65

List of figures

Figure 1. 1 ZeroW at a glance (Image provided by the Project Coordinator).....	10
Figure 2. ZeroW approach (Image provided by the Project Coordinator).....	10
Figure 3. ZeroW Goal (Source: Deliverable 7.1)	15
Figure 4. Benefits of the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem.....	17
Figure 5. Screenshot 1 from LinkedIn promotion to join the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem.....	20
Figure 6. Screenshot 2 from LinkedIn promotion to join the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem.....	20
Figure 7. ZeroFLW Internal Webinar Screenshot.....	23
Figure 8. ZeroFLW Webinar Social Media Announcement	24
Figure 9. ZeroFLW Kick-off Meeting Agenda Screenshot.....	25
Figure 10. Screenshot of meeting agenda ZeroW Systemic Innovation Living Lab - Food Loss and Waste Monitoring and Assessment	25
Figure 11. Screenshot of meeting recording presenting Living Lab #1 - Food Loss and Waste Monitoring and Assessment.....	25
Figure 12. Screenshot from Miro during the interactive session.....	26
Figure 13. Screenshot of 2nd Ecosystem’s Meeting Agenda	27
Figure 14. Screenshot from meeting recording presenting the Efficient Food Bank Network.....	27
Figure 15. Screenshot from meeting recording presenting the Belgian Food Banks	28
Figure 16. Panellists leading the From R&D to Commercialisation Panel Discussions	29
Figure 17. Screenshot of Panel Discussion from project YouTube channel	30
Figure 18. Screenshot of Panel Discussion from From Innovation to Market: Commercialising Food Loss Waste Solutions in EU Projects from Youtube channel	31
Figure 19. Timeline and actions for Task 7.5 in the first 10 months of actions in 2022	32
Figure 20. Timeline and actions for Task 7.5 in 2023 (M12-M19).....	33
Figure 21. Deliverable 7.5 screenshot from Grant Agreement	37
Figure 22. Milestone 3 screenshot from Grant Agreement.....	37
Figure 23. Screenshot of blog post from Sisters Project EU website.....	47
Figure 24. Screenshot of ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem closed Group on LinkedIn.....	48
Figure 25. Screenshot of EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub website	49

Figure 26. Screenshot of Panel Discussion posted on Sustainable Food Systems Network (SFSN) Group 50

Figure 27. Recruitment campaign for the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem on the SFSN platform 51

Figure 28. Recruitment campaign for the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem on the LinkedIn..... 51

Figure 29. Type of participants and level of engagement in the Zero FLW Business Ecosystem 52

Figure 30. Screenshot of Commercial Partnerships training session for SILLs 53

Figure 31. Screenshot of ZeroW SILLs Showcase recording..... 54

Figure 32. F6S at EIT Next Bite: Founders Day 2025..... 55

List of tables

Table 1. Glossary of terms and acronyms used 8

Table 2. Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description 11

Table 3. Overview of the expected actions in Task 7.5 Clustering & Commercial Ecosystem Creation..... 34

Table 4. Task 7.5 Clustering & Commercial Ecosystem Creation 37

Table 5. Type of Partner Involvement 42

Table 6. Initial list of identified Sister Projects 46

Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Table 1. Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Acronym / Term	Description
CCN	Cooperation and Collaboration Network of projects set by the FOODRUS project
D&C	Dissemination & Communication
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
F2F	Farm-to-Fork
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
GA	Grant Agreement
GD-SO	Green Deal Support Office
JRC	Joint Research Centre
KO	Kick off
LM	Liaison Manager
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
SILL	Systemic Innovations Living Labs
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Lead

Executive summary

This deliverable is a result of the strategy elaborated and implemented in the Task 7.5. *Clustering & Commercial Ecosystem Creation*. This task is built under the Work Package 7, dedicated to *Exploitation, sustainability & commercialisation of project outputs*. This is an internal progress report for task 7.5, which attends to building the commercial ecosystem for ZeroWaste.

The Task 7.5 as a part of the WP7 contributes to the overall objective of this WP, namely contributing, to some extent, to the formulation of a strategy with the end goal of self-sustaining group with commercial goals, providing an interface with the market sector and space of business and market relevance analysis.

In order to fulfil its role in WP7 and attain the defined goals, Task 7.5 implements and manages the Project's commercial and business ecosystem group, named Zero FLW Business Ecosystem. This group supports ZeroW's commercial outreach and exploitation strategy and acts as a commercial eco-system cluster, constituted by pertinent and relevant sectoral actors in FLW that provide an important outreach for the project as well as a principal feedback loop from external industry and sectoral stakeholders in support of the project's commercial ambitions.

ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem, in the context of the Task 7.5, is built as the backbone supporting ZeroW commercial outreach and exploitation strategy, creating a space that gathers and favours interconnections of project partners and SILLs with external stakeholders, in a group with representative of the FLW industry, customers, client stakeholders and consumer interest groups. Therefore, key third-party actors that are target as members have to be part of a broad cross section of representative of the FLW industry, as well as customers, client stakeholders and consumer interest groups, adding their diverse and relevant views from the market.

The main goal of the Zero FLW Business Ecosystem group is to keep the Project's outputs and commercial ambitions aligned with the trends, needs and expectations of the market this will be made through the interactions that are planned and aligned in an action plan presented and explored by the F6S during the following document. The ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem, as a dedicated 'community' for the consortium, enables a broad outreach to the commercial and business arena implemented several tolls, namely a digital interaction platform and planned bimonthly meetings, working as an interface with the FLW sectoral industry experts.

The outreach strategy and implementation will be reenforced as the project advances, namely privileging the co-creation process with its members, and engaging the project's partners along the process as fundamental part of the success. Partner and SILL's are an added value to this group, namely due to their broad network and expertise. The goal is that this group has a life beyond the lifespan of ZeroW project, as a seed that will be planted by the project and will carry on, growing, and providing added value to its members.

1 Introduction

1.1 ZeroW project summary aims, objectives and outputs in the context of the originating work package.

Figure 1. 1 ZeroW at a glance (Image provided by the Project Coordinator)

The ZeroW approach involves the following elements that will contribute to WP7 and T7.5 in particular:

Figure 2. ZeroW approach (Image provided by the Project Coordinator)

1.2 Mapping ZeroW outputs

The purpose of this chapter was to map ZeroW Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the current document.

Table 2. Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description

ZEROW GA Component Title	ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D7.5 Clustering and Commercial Ecosystem	The Clustering and Commercial Ecosystem Report documented and evidenced a commercial eco-system cluster and delivered an incremental ecosystem progress growth report. The report was provided in three versions: an internal Version 1 in M12, an internal Version 2 in M30, and a final version in M46.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vision and strategy creation were addressed in Chapter 1 and its corresponding subchapter, 1.2, which covered the vision, objectives, and strategy. Actions to implement the strategy were detailed in Chapter 2, specifically in the action plan and timelines. The timeline for action implementation and development, along with the responsible and co-responsible parties, were also outlined in Chapter 2 and its subchapters. Synergies and the tools for engaging the target audience were described in Chapter 3 on synergies and Chapter 4, which focused on the organization and implementation of the project. 	This final version of the document documented the completed process for creating and promoting a commercial ecosystem cluster. Unlike the initial planning versions, this report detailed the preliminary results and achievements of the implemented strategies and actions. It provided a comprehensive overview of the progress toward Task 7.5 goals, highlighting the synergies that were forged, the tools that were utilised, and the initial outcomes that were attained during the project's growth.
TASKS			

<p>T7.5 Clustering & Commercial Ecosystem Creation</p>	<p>In this Task, the Project's commercial eco-system cluster was created and managed. This acted as the backbone supporting ZeroW's commercial outreach and exploitation strategy, both during and after the project. More specifically, Task 7.5 took responsibility for substantiating a commercial eco-system cluster of pertinent and relevant sectoral actors, who supported and informed Tasks 7.1-7.3. This provided an important outreach for the project as well as a principal feedback loop from external industry and sectoral actors in support of the project's commercial ambitions.</p> <p>The principal goal of the cluster was to keep the Project's outputs and commercial ambitions sector-calibrated and market-relevant. Hence, key third-party actors that were onboarded in the cluster included a broad cross section of representative industry, customers, client stakeholders, and consumer interest groups. A broad outreach was also planned to interface the cluster with sectoral industry experts as the project made progress, thus fostering early and important relationships with the project's partners and, pertinently, incentivising both the licensing and commercial ambitions of the project by identifying, targeting, and encouraging client adopters at a Pan-EU scale. The eco-system cluster represented a self-sustaining vehicle that would continue after the project had ended. This cluster was built and managed within the project's team space, as a dedicated 'community' for the consortium.</p>	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The creation and management of commercial eco-system clusters were detailed in the following chapters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chapter 1: Introduction and its subchapter 1.2 on Vision, objectives, and strategy. • The following subchapters of Chapter 1. • Chapter 2: Action plan and timeline. 2. The document described how the initiative acted as the backbone, supporting ZeroW's commercial outreach and exploitation strategy both during and after the project. This was detailed in the following chapters: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chapter 1: Introduction and its point 1.2 on Vision, objectives, and strategy. • The following subchapters within point 1. 3. Task 7.5 took responsibility for substantiating a commercial eco-system cluster of pertinent and relevant sectoral actors. These actors supported and informed Tasks 7.1-7.3, thus providing an important outreach for the project as well as a 	<p>The main goal of this task was to create and manage a commercial ecosystem cluster that supported ZeroW's commercial outreach and exploitation strategy. Therefore, the document addressed the vision and strategy for this creation, as well as it presented the actions that led the way for engaging key sectoral actors who supported and enabled this commercial ecosystem cluster. This could be verified not only in the communication subchapter, as it provided tools to implement the interface platform described in Chapters 2, 3, and 4. This chapter showed how the strategy enabled the outputs to not only reach their commercial ambitions but also allowed the key third-party actors to jointly create an environment that kept the members sector-calibrated and market-relevant.</p>
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		<p>principal feedback loop from external industry and sectoral actors in support of the project's commercial ambitions. This was stated in Chapter 3, Synergies, in section 3.1, regarding the inputs for Work Packages, and also in the 1.2 Strategy chapter.</p> <p>4. Key third-party actors that were onboarded in the cluster included a broad cross-section of representative industry, customers, client stakeholders, and consumer interest groups. This was detailed in the following chapters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chapter 1: Introduction, specifically subchapter 1.2.2 on Strategy. • Chapter 3: Synergies. • Chapter 4: Organisation and Implementation. <p>5. A broad outreach was also planned to interface the cluster with sectoral industry experts as the project made progress, thus fostering early and important relationships with the project's partners. This was detailed in the following chapters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chapter 1: Introduction, 	
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		<p>specifically subchapter 1.2.2 on Strategy.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chapter 3: Synergies. • Chapter 4: Organisation and Implementation. <p>6. The eco-system cluster represented a self-sustaining vehicle that would continue after the project had ended. This was documented in the following chapters:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Chapter 1.2: Vision, Objectives and Strategy • Subchapter 1.2.1: Objectives & Vision 	
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1.3 Vision, Objectives and Strategy

1.3.1 Objectives & Vision

Task 7.5. *Clustering & Commercial Ecosystem Creation*, led by F6S with the participation of the following partners; Inlecom Commercial Pathways (ICP), Nederlandse Organisatie Voor Toegepast Natuurwetenschappelijk Onderzoek (TNO), DigiTouch Ou (DIGI), Konnecta Systems Limited (KNT), Inovacijsko Tehnološki Grozd Murska Sobota (ITC), Fundacion Corporacion Tecnologica De Andalucia (FCTA), Instituto Andaluz De Investigaciony Formacion Agraria Pesquera Alimentaria Y De Produccion Ecologica (IFAPA), and Agrifood Lithuania (AFL), was focused on identifying stakeholders and practical exploitation in the market, and keeping SILLs industry-calibrated. The goal was to align and integrate Task 7.5 strategy in the project strategy, to contribute to implement ZeroW practices in the market and reach people’s lives by tackling key aspects of the Food Loss & Waste (FLW).

Figure 3. ZeroW Goal (Source: Deliverable 7.1)

Figure 3, sourced and created in the context of the deliverable 7.1, identified the ZeroW goals, as following:

- **Goal 1** aimed to (i) provide a stimulating environment for SILLs innovations to thrive; (ii) address specific innovation maturity gaps to enable innovative solutions testing and demonstration; (iii) manage SILLs and support their activities from ideation to demonstration, through organised feedback rounds; (iv) enable coherent communication between ZeroW SILLs and the impact assessment, scaling-up, commercialisation and policy support activities; (v) enable evolution of SILLs from initial baseline to a higher level of systemic innovation readiness.
- **Goal 2** aimed to provide digital support for both ZeroW SILLs and future external users and solution developers working to reduce FLW.
- **Goal 3** focused on development of data driven FLW intelligent services, to be used also by external users.
- **Goal 4** aimed to employ 3 assessment perspectives: (i) Systemic Innovation Readiness Level (SIRL) to assess the extent that the SILLs systemic innovations were improving over the course of the project; (ii) Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA) to evaluate the environmental, social, and economic impacts of the SILLs during the project; (iii) Just Transition of the SILLs, implying the cost-benefit allocation to different FSC actors.
- **Goal 5** focused on scale-up of the FLW systemic innovation solutions and approach, building capacity towards near-zero FLW, stimulating investment in FLW reduction by private and public actors.
- **Goal 6** targets: (i) articulate a business- and market-relevant exploitation strategy; (ii) anchor the exploitation, business models, licensing models and go-to-market strategy via robust market sector analyses and commercial solution alignment imperatives.
- **Goal 7** aimed to deliver short- and medium-term FLW policy recommendations, namely by: (i) scaling up the ZeroW SILLs results to 2030 and 250 utilising data-driven scenarios; (ii) applying Farm-to-Fork FLW economic model to make a qualitative assessment of the alternative policies

by 2050, taking into account several factors, such as FSC business practices, consumer behaviour, anticipated FLW innovations, FLW valorisation initiatives, just profit allocations amongst FSC actors, as well as FSC coordination and risk management principles.

- **Goal 8** aimed to maximise the impact of the ZeroW results both during and beyond the project's duration, by engaging with relevant EU, National and global initiatives, as well as developing and deploying appropriate dissemination and communication strategies.

We analysed the goals of the project described above considering the Task 7.5 role and its direct and indirect impact and contribution to fulfil them. By doing so, we ended up **focusing specifically on three of them**, which were:

- **Goal 1:** Task 7.5 created and managed the Ecosystem, from which SILLs benefitted and improved. The ecosystem was an environment that helped boost readiness for systemic innovation, especially from a commercial standpoint. Moreover, the Ecosystem provided feedback, in terms of market relevance and consumers/investors needs and expectations. The ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem also enabled a business/commercial environment in which SILLs innovations thrived;
- **Goal 5:** The ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem facilitated networking centred around business and commercialisation of solutions. This environment was set to stimulate investment in FLW reduction by both private and public actors, supporting the commercialisation and eventual scaling up of project's innovative solutions within designated macro regions;
- **Goal 6:** Task 7.5 conducted activities that gathered market sector insights, as well as identified key factors such as customer needs, competitive landscape, regulatory considerations, and market trends. Moreover, the task involved identifying and addressing alignment priorities between the project's solutions and the European commercial landscape.

The goals of the initiatives under the scope of the Task 7.5, namely the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem, were to promote the stakeholder's engagement, as a result of synergies, networking, and knowledge access. Additionally, the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem Group actively managed and facilitated the activities to achieve the ecosystem's goals, such as building a bridge between products and the market and creating a space for direct know-how exchange among key actors, enabling a context that promotes innovation creation, commercialisation and business connections. F6S created and managed a community for ZeroW that promoted access to know-how exchange of information, directly from the key actors about the needs, trends and opportunities in the market through the exchange of ideas, information, networking, etc.

Grant Agreement no. 101036388

Figure 4. Benefits of the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem

Some of the benefits of the stakeholder participation comes out of the goals that were set for this group and in the above image (Fig 4). The target stakeholders for the Zero FLW Business Ecosystem group, was divided into: Project partners & SILLs; External Business/Commercial stakeholders and AB Members. The vision was that the benefits of the group’s members are transversal to all.

The **main benefits** that the group provided, and tackled were the following, with no particular priority:

- Discovered and collaborated with investors and potential business partners to explore commercial opportunities;
- Developed strategies to identify and present innovative solutions tailored to market demands;
- Gained deeper understanding of the FLW market's requirements and trends;
- Stayed actively involved in the exchange of valuable information;
- Fostered networking, synergies, and meaningful discourse with strategic partners and peers.

The initial goal was to create a group of **at least 50 relevant members** in the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem by M12. This goal was achieved by broadening the initial target to encompass all areas of FLW. However, considering the diverse range of areas being explored within the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem group, specific clusters within the ZeroW project were targeted for inclusion. Upon the creation of the group, an analysis was conducted to identify these clusters, and this information was internally presented to ZeroW project partners. A communication strategy was then developed, focusing on aligning collaboration efforts with leaders from WP10 and WP9 within the project.

The growth of the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem proceeded incrementally, with contributions from both its members and the support of project cluster partners, and campaigns as outlined in Chapter 3 of the document. A new goal was then set to **expand the group to include 100 members**, with a strategic focus on engaging various stakeholders across different sectors, including:

- **Industry Partners.** Engaging with businesses involved in food production, processing, distribution, and retail to address FLW challenges at each stage of the supply chain.
- **Government Agencies.** Collaborating with regulatory bodies and policymakers to implement policies and initiatives that reduce FLW and promote sustainable practices.
- **Nonprofit Organisations.** Cooperating with NGOs and charitable organisations to address social and environmental aspects of FLW, such as food insecurity and waste management.
- **Research Institutions.** Working with academic institutions and research centres to conduct studies, develop innovative solutions, and disseminate knowledge on FLW reduction strategies.

Once the new goal of achieving 100 members within the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem was successfully reached, the initiative embraced a new phase of expansion and inclusion. This milestone marked a significant turning point in the ecosystem's journey, showcasing its readiness to engage a broader spectrum of stakeholders and enhance its influence within the FLW domain.

Having surpassed the initial goal, the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem has onboarded 117 members as of M30. Following this achievement, members with expertise in commercialisation were actively sought to further enrich the diverse community. Leveraging the momentum gained from exceeding the initial target, the initiative boosted its outreach efforts to engage individuals and organisations from various sectors and geographic regions. This emphasis aimed to develop collaboration, innovation, and promote knowledge exchange among stakeholders dedicated to advancing solutions for reducing FLW. By the submission of this deliverable (M46), the **ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem has onboarded a total of 129 members**.

1.3.2 Ecosystem set-up and member engagement strategy

The ecosystem interacted primarily through a closed LinkedIn Group, and online meetings that first happened bi-monthly and then quarterly. These meetings facilitated group discussions, with members co-creating content as expert representatives in the FLW sector. F6S managed and facilitated both the group and the meetings.

In those meetings, the group discussed several thematic topics selected based on feedback from a questionnaire circulated to potential members of the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem. The topics included Packaging Solutions, Post-Harvesting

Challenges, Energy, Transport and Supply Chain, and Consumer Engagement. Additionally, ZeroW project team members aimed to explore new areas such as Digital Transformation in FLW, Innovations in Food Waste Reduction, Policy and Regulation Impact, Circular Economy Practices, Sustainable Business Models, Collaboration and Partnership Opportunities, and Barriers in Commercialising FLW Innovations. These discussions fostered a comprehensive understanding and collaborative approach towards addressing the challenges and opportunities in the FLW sector.

The strategy of the Zero FLW Business Ecosystem was to engage, approach content creation and strengthen bridges/connections between members to:

1. Engage key stakeholder in the **cluster/ ecosystem, on FLW, in the area of commercialisation;**
2. Create a **discussion** group;
3. Promote **networking**.

The implementation of these points was approached and developed in more detail on the actions plan (2.1) subchapter, as the implementation methodology of the defined strategy. The group had been formed initially with the enrolled external stakeholders with direct or indirect interest in FLW, with a commercial/business profile or interest. These external stakeholders were enrolled in the context of expression of interest, recommendation, or direct request.

Campaigns for **Expressions of Interest** were launched regularly, as "**artificial cohorts**." These cohorts were designated periods with a specific launch date and enrolment deadline, promoted through social networks, the website, and with the support of ZeroW project partners. Members of the group were also asked to disseminate and promote these campaigns. The cohorts acted as a marketing tool to grab attention, create urgency, encourage enrolment, and highlight group activities. In practical terms, **enrolment remained open continuously**, which allowed new members to join at any time either by direct request from interested stakeholders or through recommendations from members, partners, or a SILL.

The profiles primarily pertained to businesses, commercial entities, clusters, NGOs in FLW, food banks, and consumer associations interested in integrating or deepening their involvement in the commercial sector and establishing business connections. Partners and SILLs were also encouraged to enrol, even though they were invited to participate in the initiatives promoted by the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem, although their participation remained voluntary.

Figure 5. Screenshot 1 from LinkedIn promotion to join the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem

Figure 6. Screenshot 2 from LinkedIn promotion to join the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem

The first Expression of Interest was launched on October 6, 2022, through ZeroW's social media and website. This was the inaugural Expression of Interest, with subsequent campaigns that were planned at least every six months as F6S continued to create new cohorts for recruiting members. These Expressions of Interests were a communication and marketing strategy (Fig 5 and Fig 6) that was designed to create urgency and catch the attention of the FLW community. In practice, the group remained open between cohorts, which allowed partners, group members, and SILLs to recommend new members at any time, either during the Expression of Interest periods or between them.

The list of stakeholders enrolled through all the Expressions of Interest is available in the **Appendix I**.

The goal was to focus communication on relevant stakeholders who added value to the network and discussions in the business, investment, and FLW markets, particularly within the SILLs and clusters. Therefore, the message emphasised benefits and goals, targeting the broader FLW community while **prioritising commercial and business profiles**. Over time, communication was adjusted to address specific areas where the group lacked representation, based on the SILLs and clusters of the ZeroW project.

2 Main Actions and Timelines

To ensure relevant and actionable stakeholder engagement, several phases were implemented over the course of the project. This chapter outlines the **evolution of the stakeholder engagement strategy**, detailing the key activities carried out from the project's inception through its conclusion, spanning beyond M30. It provides a comprehensive overview of the approaches used, their outcomes, and the lessons learned to inform future initiatives. The first section outlines the foundational work and key milestones achieved during the initial phases of the project (before Month 30). This includes the establishment of our engagement framework and the successful implementation of our initial action plans. The subsequent section looks ahead, providing a strategic outlook for our activities beyond Month 30. It details the upcoming action plans, future initiatives, and next steps.

2.1 Main Actions

The stakeholder engagement activities were structured into multiple phases throughout the project. The first phase, from M3 to M12, focused on Ecosystem Establishment, laying the foundation for meaningful collaboration. This was followed by an eight-month action plan from M12 to M19, aimed at implementation and the achievement of early results. From M19 to M30, the emphasis shifted to Ecosystem Enhancement and the gathering of insights to strengthen engagement strategies.

In the final phase of the project (M31 to M46), efforts concentrated on consolidating the ecosystem and ensuring long-term impact. Key activities during this period included the Commercial Partnership Training Session, the ZeroW Business Ecosystem SILLs Showcase, and the ZeroW Final Event Pitching Session. Additionally, several Business Ecosystem meetings were held to maintain momentum, foster collaboration, and facilitate knowledge exchange among stakeholders.

The benefits of having participated in the Zero FLW Business Ecosystem group were activated through the implementation of the following strategy, executed via these main actions:

- **Engaged Key Stakeholders** in the Cluster/Ecosystem on FLW Commercialisation:
 - Built a contact list by gathering organisations previously identified and interested through other tasks and work packages, particularly Task 7.1 and WP9.
 - Directly contacted organisations identified by F6S, WP leaders, partners, SILLs, and synergy partners.
- **Created a Discussion Group:**
 - Launched an Expression of Interest campaign which attracted external stakeholders to the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem group,

using communication and marketing strategies via LinkedIn, the project's website, newsletters, and the F6S and partners' websites and social media.

- Established a closed LinkedIn group and provided a common space for partners to communicate, exchange ideas and information, organised and promoted events/meetings, and created discussion content.
- Organised and participate in meetings to discuss opportunities and best practices. These meetings addressed relevant themes, decided through a pre-circulated questionnaire among members, ensuring the meetings were pertinent to FLW needs and engaging for participants.
- **Promote Networking:**
 - Encouraged networking and expanded the ecosystem view by using the aforementioned tools (meetings and digital platform) and provided information about face-to-face or online events.

To reach external stakeholders, a communication kit was created and disseminated among ZeroW partners and SILLs to facilitate contact with their networks.

2.1.1 Main Actions (M3–M12)

We can summarise that four specific actions were taken to **initially engage stakeholders** in the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem:

ACTION 1: On October 6th, 2022, a public **Expression of Interest** was launched through the ZeroW website and social networks, as well as through the channels of other project partners. F6S primarily promoted this Expression of Interest via the ZeroW social network and website, with strong support from ZeroW partners, particularly the WP10 Leader.

Figure 7. ZeroFLW Internal Webinar Screenshot

ACTION 2: F6S organised an **internal webinar** (Fig 7) on November 3rd, 2022, to explain Task 7.5 and the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem group, which detailed its objectives, benefits, structure, organisation, and targeted stakeholders to partners and SILLs. During the event, a Google Form was presented to gather inputs on themes, levels of participation, and suggestions. F6S requested their participation in the group and encouraged dissemination within their networks. A recording of the meeting was shared internally in the ZeroW project.

ACTION 3: A **public webinar** (Fig 8) was organised on November 17th, 2022, to present the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem under the ZeroW umbrella, which detailed its objectives, benefits, structure, organisation, and targeted stakeholders. A Google Form was presented during the event to collect inputs on themes, levels of participation, and suggestions. F6S invited participants to join the group and encouraged them to disseminate the opportunity within their networks. A recording of the webinar was made available and shared with participants as a communication and dissemination tool. After Actions 2 and 3, F6S analysed **questionnaires** and created future action plans based on the results. Refer to **Appendix II** for results from this survey.

Grant Agreement no. 101036388

Figure 8. ZeroFLW Webinar Social Media Announcement

ACTION 4: A Virtual Kick-off Event (Fig 9) was organised on December 7th, 2022, to initiate group activities, foster networking, and kick-start discussions. The project was presented at a high level, along with the group's objectives. A Miro board discussion was created to facilitate sharing ideas, thoughts, and work, particularly in assessing expectations and preparing for subsequent meetings. The expected outcome of the kick-off was to generate engagement and network growth, as well as valuable idea exchange. This marked the first step towards co-creating content and developing work progress and strategy in alignment with the interests of ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem members.

The anticipated outcome of the kick-off event was to foster engagement and expand the network, while also facilitating valuable idea exchange. This event marks the initial stage in collaboratively generating content and advancing the work and strategy aligned with the interests of ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem members.

Figure 9. ZeroFLW Kick-off Meeting Agenda Screenshot

2.1.2 Main Actions (M12–M19)

The **First ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem meeting** was held on 22 February 2023, centred around the topic of "ZeroW Systemic Innovation Living Lab: Food Loss and Waste Monitoring and Assessment" (Fig 10 and Fig 11). The meeting commenced with an insightful presentation of SILL #1 by Andra Tănase (ATIT), followed by two engaging Q&A sessions, one focused on the SILL and the other on the broader thematic topic.

Figure 10. Screenshot of meeting agenda ZeroW Systemic Innovation Living Lab - Food Loss and Waste Monitoring and Assessment

Figure 11. Screenshot of meeting recording presenting Living Lab #1 - Food Loss and Waste Monitoring and Assessment

With a total of 43 participants actively involved, the meeting facilitated interactive opinion sharing via Miro (Fig 12), creating a collaborative environment for exploring innovative approaches to address challenges related to food loss and waste (FLW).

Figure 12. Screenshot from Miro during the interactive session

The Miro board was used as a collaborative canvas, capturing input from participants on a range of topics. Group members actively contributed their insights on challenges, opportunities, and innovative solutions/projects related to the thematic focus. Additionally, discussions revolved around identifying strategies to address challenges and leverage opportunities within the thematic framework. Furthermore, participants expressed their preferences regarding the type of information they would like shared with them on this thematic, facilitating a comprehensive understanding of their collective interests and priorities.

During the dynamic exchange of ideas, participants explored key themes such as technological advancements, data collection methodologies, and performance metrics. The discussion also touched upon the integration of technologies and solutions for real-time monitoring and traceability of food supply chains. Additionally, considerations were raised regarding the importance of standardised metrics and indicators to enable meaningful comparisons and benchmarking across different initiatives and regions.

Throughout the discussion, group members leveraged their diverse expertise and experiences to critically evaluate existing approaches and propose strategies for enhancing FLW monitoring and assessment practices.

On April 25, 2023, the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem convened for its second meeting (Fig 13 and Fig 14), diving into the theme of **efficient food bank networks** and drawing insights from the experiences of Belgian food banks. The meeting commenced with a presentation by Renzo Akkerman, the SILL Coordinator from WUR, who provided an in-depth overview of efficient food bank networks within the context of the ZeroW Systemic Innovation Living Lab (SILL).

Figure 13. Screenshot of 2nd Ecosystem's Meeting Agenda

Figure 14. Screenshot from meeting recording presenting the Efficient Food Bank Network

The presentation offered valuable insights into innovative strategies and best practices aimed at optimising food bank operations, aligning with the ecosystem's overarching goal of reducing food loss and waste. Following the presentation delivered by Renzo Akkerman, participants engaged in an interactive Q&A session, fostering dialogue and exchange of ideas on the topic of efficient food bank networks. This section provided attendees with the opportunity to seek clarification, share perspectives, and explore potential solutions collaboratively. Transitioning to a Miro board session, participants continued their exploration of the meeting's theme through digital collaboration. The Miro board acted as a platform for brainstorming and idea sharing, enabling participants to contribute their insights, suggestions, and feedback on challenges, opportunities, and innovative solutions related to the efficient functioning of food bank networks. The meeting further featured a presentation by Etienne Rubens, representing the Belgian Federation of

Foodbanks (Fig 15), who shared insights into the experiences and practices of Belgian food banks. Etienne's presentation offered a comparative analysis and real-world examples, enriching the discussion on food bank operations and collaboration within the FLW ecosystem.

Figure 15. Screenshot from meeting recording presenting the Belgian Food Banks

The meeting concluded with a second interactive Q&A session, providing participants with the opportunity to deepen their understanding of key insights from the presentations and engage in further discussion.

2.1.3 Main Actions (M19–M30)

Following the second meeting, it was decided to organise a panel discussion instead of convening another meeting, with a particular emphasis on attracting panellists with expertise in commercialisation. This strategic decision was driven by plans to host a public panel discussion in 2024, centred around the theme of "R&D to Commercialisation." Recognising the role of this event in advancing discussions on food loss and waste solutions, the primary goal was to ensure the success of the panel discussion by securing panel members who could offer the appropriate expertise and insights and addressing the complexities of FLW reduction and sustainable practices, while also facilitating the continued growth of the ecosystem.

The public panel discussion, "From R&D to Commercialisation: Challenges and Strategies for Food Loss and Waste Innovative Technologies," took place on March 27, 2024. The event drew significant interest, with a total of 71 registrations and 35 participants in attendance. Notably, 16 new individuals expressed keen interest in joining the Ecosystem, showcasing the event's impact in expanding community engagement.

Panellists (Fig 16) Stephan Bostoën, Miguel Angel Cubero Márquez, and Colin Keogh led insightful discussions focused on the transition of innovative FLW technologies to commercialisation. Throughout the session, key insights emerged, shedding light on critical aspects of this transition process.

Figure 16. Panellists leading the From R&D to Commercialisation Panel Discussions

The discussion highlighted the multifaceted challenges inherent in transitioning innovative FLW technologies. Panellists emphasised the need for robust funding and iterative development processes, underlining the importance of achieving critical mass and aligning value chains. Moreover, they addressed the challenge of identifying genuine market needs, highlighting the necessity of market research and validation.

Strategic partnerships emerged as a pivotal facilitator in this transition journey. Panellists stressed the importance of cohesive collaborations between academia, industry, government, and stakeholders. They emphasised the significance of soliciting end-user feedback, adapting to market demands, and embracing calculated risks to foster innovation.

The role of funding mechanisms and investment opportunities was also explored in depth. Panellists discussed how early-stage investment plays a crucial role in bridging the gap between innovation and market readiness. They highlighted the necessity of judicious risk assessment and the importance of leveraging diverse funding sources to mitigate financial risks and ensure sustainable growth.

Ensuring market-readiness and meeting end-user needs emerged as key priorities. Panellists emphasised the iterative refinement process, which involves trial and error, end-user validation, and industry trials. They stressed the importance of agility, adaptability, and continuous improvement in responding to market dynamics and evolving consumer preferences.

Long-term sustainability and impact were central themes of the discussion. Panellists emphasised the need to establish robust business models and strive for self-sufficiency. They emphasised the need to keep pushing forward and bouncing back, stressing the importance of staying resilient. They also talked about taking a

comprehensive approach that values environmental, social, and economic sustainability.

Figure 17. Screenshot of Panel Discussion from project YouTube channel

Overall, the panel discussion provided valuable insights and actionable strategies for transitioning innovative FLW technologies to commercialisation, further advancing the ZeroW Project's mission to address food loss and waste challenges sustainably. The recording of the panel discussion can be viewed on the [ZeroW Project YouTube channel](#) (Fig 17).

2.1.4 Main Actions (M30–M48)

During this period, the focus was refined for the ecosystem's strategy. This involved reviewing and adjusting the strategy and action plan based on feedback, lessons learned, and evolving project requirements. Stakeholder consultations and engagement sessions were conducted to gather insights and inputs for enhancing the strategy. Additionally, the strategy document was updated to reflect any changes in project priorities, market dynamics, or stakeholder needs, ensuring alignment with the project's evolving context and objectives.

ZeroW successfully hosted a panel discussion titled "From Innovation to Market: Commercialising Food Loss Waste Solutions in EU Projects," which centered on the commercialisation of innovative solutions developed within EU-funded projects.

Figure 18. Screenshot of Panel Discussion from *From Innovation to Market: Commercialising Food Loss Waste Solutions in EU Projects* from Youtube channel

To ensure a fruitful discussion, F6S and partners first identified relevant projects through research and consultation with industry experts. Invitations were then extended to project coordinators and key personnel to participate as panellists. The discussion was structured around key themes, including the challenges and barriers encountered when bringing innovations to market, as well as success stories and effective strategies.

The workshop attracted significant interest, with 108 total registrants from 38 countries, ultimately drawing 53 participants. Notably, the largest groups of attendees were from Spain, Belgium, Germany, Greece, and the United Kingdom, highlighting the event's broad geographical reach. Following the discussion, 25 participants expressed interest in joining the Ecosystem, a strong indicator of the event's success in engaging new stakeholders.

As part of the final event, a dedicated pitching session was held on 16th September to assess the investment readiness of the SILLs. The session was moderated by F6S and featured Arne Hautekiet from Astanor Ventures as the sole investor and assessor. Eight SILLs participated, each presenting their solutions in a concise format followed by a Q&A segment. This activity formed a key part of the investment support provided during the project. More detailed information on the design, preparation, and outcomes of this session was included in Deliverable D6.3.

2.2 Timeline and Strategy

A first version of the strategic plan was presented to partners as part of Work Package 7 in May 2022 (M5). This plan was developed to guide the project's goals and actions from M3 to M46.

To manage this multi-year scope, an annual plan was created that detailed the step-by-step actions for 2022, which initiated the process for Task 7.5: Clustering and

Commercial Ecosystem Creation. We also assessed the actions for the following eight months (M12 to M19), providing a clear preview of the implementation steps that followed this initial period of preparation and strategy.

Actions timeline for Task 7.5 in 2022

Figure 19. Timeline and actions for Task 7.5 in the first 10 months of actions in 2022

The timeline is aligned with the goals of the Task 7.5 and intends to engage internal and external stakeholders that can benefit from the Zero FLW Ecosystem group.

Below are the key activities that have been executed for Task 7.5 in the period of M3 to M12:

- **6th October 2022**- Launched the campaign for the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem.
All partners were asked to share (prepare information with text for an article to post (with WP10) on the website and social media posts) in their websites and social networks - The campaign launched about 2 months before the Kick off date;
- **3rd November 2022**- SILLs and partner session was held about the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem (awareness and engaging event);
- **17th November 2022** - Webinar, Public session was held about the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem (coordinator spoke about the project; WP7; Task 7.5- ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem);
- **7th December 2022** - Kick-off ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem was delivered (with the enrolled members, internal and external and partners with PM in WP7).
- **7th December 2022** - Launched the closed LinkedIn group by F6S;

The first six months following the project's kick-off, beginning at M12, marked the start of actions for the Zero FLW Business Ecosystem Group. This period was

focused on creating content and activities to keep the group active and engaged. The two main tools for interaction were the group's digital platform, a closed LinkedIn group, and a series of meetings that took place with enrolled members, partners, and SILLs who were interested in participating. A corresponding timeline summarised and highlighted the continuation of these activities, such as the synergies and meetings that took place after the kick-off in M12.

Actions timeline for Task 7.5 in 2023 (M12-M19)

Figure 20. Timeline and actions for Task 7.5 in 2023 (M12-M19)

Below are the milestones carried out for activity to take place in Task 7.5 for the period of M12 to M19;

- **February 2023 (M14)** – First meeting for the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem (awareness and engaging event);
- **April 2023 (M16)** - Second meeting for the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem (awareness and engaging event);
- **June 2023 (M18)** – Third meeting for the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem (awareness and engaging event).
- **June to July 2023 (M18-M19)** – Internal meeting (with partners and SILLs of the ZeroW) of engagement, awareness, conclusions from previous meetings, and debate about the first 6 months of the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem activities
- **July 2023 (M19)** – Launched a campaign for new members to join the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem (to run for 3 months)

The two main tools managed by F6S and provided to the members of the Zero FLW Business Ecosystem group to reach the goal of Task 7.5 were the meetings and the closed LinkedIn group. These tools were intended to steer the way toward an enabling environment for business and the creation of ideas, which was stimulated

by F6S with the support of the ZeroW partners and SILLs. F6S also sought the support of other FLW platforms, such as sister projects, that could contribute as experts and add value to the discussions and interactions.

A corresponding table presented below is an overview of the expected actions. It listed and explained what the actions were about, their timeline and regularity, the responsibility for their implementation and leadership, and the expected outcomes of those actions.

Table 3. Overview of the expected actions in Task 7.5 Clustering & Commercial Ecosystem Creation

Action	Timeline/regularity	Responsible for implementation /lead	Participants	Expected outcome
Kick-off meeting	Kick-Off Meeting (Dec 22) Introduction to the ZeroW Project, followed by an explanation of the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem and its associated expectations. A thematic discussion on the Food Supply Chain ensued, facilitating knowledge exchange. Finally, the establishment of meeting frequency and expectations for future engagements.	F6S	Members of the group	Shared understanding among participants regarding the objectives and structure of the ZeroW Project, the roles and expectations within the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem, insights into the Food Supply Chain thematic discussion, and clarity on meeting frequency and expectations for ongoing engagement.
Define thematic of future meetings	Thematic voting (Feb 23) A thematic voting poll will be open in the LinkedIn group. F6S will post, analyse results and decide on the thematic/subject to be presented.	F6S	Members of the group/ SILL's can suggest the pool thematic	Define a thematic that resonates with the majority of the group and guarantees a considerable turnout.

Delivery of first meeting	1st Meeting (Feb 23) SILL: FLW Monitoring and Assessment	F6S/ SILL Coordinators	Members of the group	Presentation from the SILL, followed by an in-depth discussion within the group on the topic of FLW Monitoring and Assessment.
Delivery of second meeting	2nd Meeting (Apr 23) SILL: Efficient Food Bank Network Belgian Food Banks	F6S/ SILL Coordinators	Members of the group	Engage in a dynamic Miro board session alongside Q&A sessions, exploring the presentation on the Efficient Food Bank Network by SILL, with valuable contributions from Belgian Food Banks. This interactive platform encourages collaborative brainstorming and knowledge exchange, facilitating the enhancement of food bank networks.
Delivery of first Public Panel discussion	1st Public Panel Discussion (Mar 24) From R&D to Commercialisation: Challenges and Strategies for Food Loss and Waste Innovative Technologies	F6S	Members of the group/ Guest Speakers	Participants gain insights into challenges transitioning innovative technologies from R&D to commercialisation in FLW, fostering effective strategies and facilitating successful implementation.
Lead and facilitate the meetings/ Panel Discussions	Future meetings/ Panel discussions (as per needed/ every 4 months) (Ongoing)	F6S	Members of the group/ Guest Speakers	Initiate and facilitate discussions, both in small and large groups, foster networking opportunities, facilitate the

				exchange of innovative information and ideas, and cultivate an environment conducive to fostering business and commercial partnerships.
ZeroW Heroes	Identify ZeroW Heroes	F6S	Members of the group	This initiative is to recognise and promote individuals reducing food waste. Participants will share their motivations, progress, future goals, and encouragement for collective efforts through video responses. These videos will be edited and shared on social media to inspire others and drive widespread action against food loss and waste.
Post articles and opportunities; news and other information of interest in the closed LinkedIn group	An average of 1 or 2 posts bi-weekly from M12 onwards	F56; group members; partners in the project	F6S; partners; SILL (in a volunteer base); Sister projects (in a volunteer base); members of the Zero FLW Ecosystem Group	Engage and stimulate debate, provide added value, and exchange information with business and investment interests.

2.3 Deliverable & Milestone timeline and objective

Internal versions of the strategy and action plan for T7.5 were developed at M12 and M30, with the final delivery of Deliverable D.7.5 at M46 which represented a significant milestone, encapsulating valuable insights and outcomes relevant to the project's objectives.

Deliverable Number ¹⁴	Deliverable Title	Lead beneficiary	Type ¹⁵	Dissemination level ¹⁶	Due Date (in months) ¹⁷
D7.5	Clustering and Commercial Ecosystem	30 - F6S IE	Report	Public	46

Figure 21. Deliverable 7.5 screenshot from Grant Agreement

D7.5: Clustering and Commercial Ecosystem was the fifth deliverable from WP7 which was due for submission in M46, to be submitted in the form of a report. It's previewed two internal versions before the final version was submitted, with the following timeline:

- Version 1: The document and evidence of a commercial eco-system cluster delivered an incremental ecosystem progress growth report was submitted in M12;
- Version 2: Submitted the internal version 2 in M30;
- Version 3: This document is the final version to be submitted in M46, as a public report.

Milestone number ¹⁸	Milestone title	Lead beneficiary	Due Date (in months)	Means of verification
MS3	Commercial Eco System Cluster (50+ relevant organisations) established	1 - ICP	12	D7.5_v1 delivered

Figure 22. Milestone 3 screenshot from Grant Agreement

Milestone 3 (MS3) was successfully completed by its due date at Month 12. Led by **ICP**, the milestone's primary objective was to establish a **commercial eco-system cluster** with over **50 relevant organisations**. The successful achievement of this milestone was formally verified by the delivery of document D7.5_v1. The establishment of this cluster represented a crucial initial step in building a robust network of stakeholders dedicated to the commercialisation of food loss and waste solutions.

2.4 Internal project set-up: partners' roles

Task 7.5 had nine partners sharing person-months during the period that the work of the task was implemented in the ZeroW project, from M3 to M46. The ZeroW project partners had shared responsibilities in Task 7.5 that assumed the following roles, described in (Table 4) in the context of their involvement, or other, in case they wanted to participate in other ways towards a successful implementation of the actions previewed in this task to reach the task goals.

Table 4. Task 7.5 Clustering & Commercial Ecosystem Creation

Partner	Role
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F6S	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As task leader, the role of this partner was to support the overall project management, define the strategy of implementation of task 7.5 through a defined set of actions towards the outcomes of the task, as defined by the GA; • F6S also implemented synergies with the WP leaders and partners, as well as external platforms for dissemination and other relevant stakeholders that brought added value to the outcomes of this task.
ICP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As WP leader, ICP supported and followed up on the F6S actions, giving valuable feedback; • Facilitated the link with relevant stakeholders when there was an opportunity to share knowledge, learned from each other, or shared SILLs results that are public that could have been of interest for the project to be shared in the group meetings; • Attended Ecosystem meetings; • Validated information to be shared with members, when requested, and answering surveys directed to members of the group.
TNO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reached out to their networks when there is an opportunity to share information or news from the Zero FLW Business Ecosystem group; • Provided F6S with constructive feedback and inputs on the strategy and on the works that are taking place in the group; • Attended the meetings as scheduled; • Validated information to be shared with members, when requested; • Answered surveys directed to members of the group, when requested.
DIGI	
KNT	
ITC	
FCTA	
IFAPA	
AFL	

The tasks for each partner were determined by the positive contributions they made and the value they added toward reaching the project goals. By contributing with some of the actions suggested, the partners were able to connect the group with their strong networks, which helped add valuable members to the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem group.

Most of the actions and engagement that were suggested were considered part of the role of any active member of the group. Additionally, partners could also reach out to F6S if they wanted to go further with their contributions, such as:

- Being a speaker or presenter at the bi-monthly meetings.
- Recommending members to be integrated into the group.

- Suggesting any other actions that they deemed fit to the task and that added value to the overall goal in Task 7.5.

3 Synergies

3.1 Internal project set-up: partners' roles

Several Work Packages of the project were key to fulfil the goals of Task 7.5. The table below described the main WP's that have a role in the development and implementation of actions in the context of this task, per phases.

Lead partner: TNO	WP2: OFLW Data Space
Implementation phase (M10-M48)	WP2 provided help regarding dissemination of the Ecosystem activities and participated and gave feedback and constructive inputs regarding the areas of discussion during the Ecosystem meetings.
Lead partner: EV ILVO	WP6: Fostering systemic innovation & building capacity towards near-zero FLW
Implementation phase (M10-M48)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provided support regarding dissemination of the group and participated and gave feedback and constructive inputs. • Promoted opportunities to connect with investors/corporates or other entities and boost their growth, either through informing about relevant FLW events, news, articles, etc.
Lead partner: ICP Task 7.5 lead: F6S	WP7: Exploitation, sustainability & commercialisation of project outputs
Preparatory phase (M3-M6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For Task 7.5 F6S along with synergies with other partners, namely WP9, constructed a stakeholder mapping with business, start-ups, innovators, and other private sector stakeholders. WP7 were also able to help based on the market analysis.
Lead partner: ICLEI EURO	WP9: Cooperation with EC services & other projects/initiatives
Implementation phase (M10-M48)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP9 strategic support to the creation of T7.5 commercial ecosystem, including through stakeholder databases,

	<p>and contributed with contacts for synergies and networking reach. Especially in the context of Task 9.3;</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provided support regarding dissemination of the group and participated and gave feedback and constructive inputs; • Promoted opportunities to connect with investors/corporates or other entities and boost their growth, either through informing about relevant FLW events, news, articles, etc.
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Lead partner: FBCD	WP10: Dissemination and communication
Preparatory phase (M3-M6)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP10 contributed to stakeholder mapping in line with D&C targets and built the communication strategy for the implementation of the Zero FLW Business Ecosystem.
Implementation phase (M7-M48)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provided strategic guidance on communication efforts to attract business stakeholders; included advice on interesting/influential media and communications channels, platforms for information sharing, as well as events and conferences to share with the group. Promoted the communication and dissemination of actions from the Zero FLW Business Ecosystem on the website, newsletter and social media networks.

3.2 Internal Project Set-up: SILLS and Clusters Roles

In the ZeroW project, **SILLS were structured into 4 Clusters**, each addressed different thematic areas:

- Cluster 1 (SILL1) focused on IT platforms,
- Cluster 2 (SILL3) on pre- and post-harvest innovation,
- Cluster 3 (SILL2, SILL4, SILL5, SILL6) on food processing innovation, and
- Cluster 4 (SILL7, SILL8, SILL9) on wholesale, retail, and consumer innovation.

The ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem engaged stakeholders aligned with these cluster groups. Furthermore, SILLs participated in these clusters who played a crucial role in disseminating information to their network of commercial stakeholders, promoting the advantages and objectives of the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem via their websites and social networks to attract relevant members.

While not all nine SILLs in the ZeroW project possess commercial profiles, they may have harboured commercial interest and had access to valuable networks with

commercial characteristics. Therefore, all SILLs stand to benefit from engaging in ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem activities.

The **engagement of SILLs** within the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem was viewed in terms of two levels: **as members and as supporters**. SILLs with commercial profiles or interests actively participated as members, while others supported the ecosystem's activities voluntarily, which contributed to its success as part of the ZeroW project, particularly when requested directly by F6S, the WP7 leader, coordinator, or for specific initiatives or actions. This inclusive approach ensured that all SILLs contributed value to the ecosystem, whether through active participation or supportive roles.

The ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem tackled stakeholders that were in the areas of the cluster groups. Also, the SILLs that took part in these clusters had a fundamental part in the success in disseminating information with their network of commercial stakeholders, namely disseminating in their websites and social networks, the advantages and goals of the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem in order to engage them in the groups and attract relevant members.

The table below outlined the engagement of SILLs within the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem, which considered their possible contributions to Task 7.5 actions and goals. This analysis considered the profile of each SILL and the suggested level of involvement, recognising that varying degrees of engagement provided added benefits for both the SILLs and the project.

The following actions highlighted areas where SILLs contributed to and benefitted from participation in the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem:

1. **Knowledge/information/experience shared** by having participated in events and sharing expertise on EU regulations, projects, and initiatives relevant to FLW management.
2. **Dissemination of relevant activities** by having promoted the ecosystem's activities from a business perspective within their area of research to their networks.
3. **Participation in Ecosystem meetings** and engaged in ecosystem activities by having attended meetings and provided input on discussion topics.
4. Contribution to thematic discussions by having **offered insights and inputs** on thematic topics discussed during meetings.

These suggestions underscored the benefits of having participated in the group and emphasised the value that SILLs brought to the project. SILLs had the flexibility to determine their level of engagement based on project timelines, the relevance of discussion topics, and other factors.

Table 5. Type of Partner Involvement

SILL number	Organisations involved	Profile	Type of involvement
1	I ITC; IIAF; UM; ATIT; ATC;	Research; NGO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Facilitating the sharing of knowledge, information, and experiences, encompassing events, EU regulations, and ongoing projects and initiatives. • Disseminating pertinent activities within the scope of their research area, with a business-oriented perspective. • Assisting in the dissemination efforts to extend outreach to their networks, particularly regarding the opening calls for enrollment in the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem group.
2	ITENE; EROSKI; TERMO; NVMT	Technological (Compartmentalised tray for oily fresh fish; Bioplastics and biochemicals company); Commercial (Retailer/Supermarket ; packaging producer)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acting as a business connector, facilitating connections and collaborations within the ecosystem. • Sharing knowledge, information, and experiences related to events, EU regulations, and ongoing projects and initiatives. • Disseminating relevant activities within their sector to enhance awareness and engagement. • Active participation in meetings and engagement in ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem activities. • Providing valuable inputs on thematic topics for discussion during meetings.

SILL number	Organisations involved	Profile	Type of involvement
3	AFL; ART21; LVPA; SFC	Technology (AFL; ART21; Non-profit organisation (LVPA; SFC); Cluster	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acting as a business connector, fostering connections and collaborations within the ecosystem. Sharing knowledge, information, and experiences related to events, EU regulations, and ongoing projects and initiatives. Disseminating pertinent activities within their sector to enhance awareness and engagement. Providing valuable inputs on thematic topics for discussion during meetings.
4	EV-ILVO; OVAM; DIL; Boerenbond and ISP; VBL; SVZ	Research (EV-ILVO; DIL); Public body (OVAM); Union (Boerenbond and ISP); Food Bank (VBL); Company (SVZ)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sharing knowledge, information, and experiences related to events, EU regulations, and ongoing projects and initiatives. Disseminating pertinent activities within their area of research, with a business-oriented perspective. Assisting in dissemination efforts to reach out to their network, particularly regarding opening calls for enrollment in the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem group.
5	CTA; GLC; MST; IFAPA	Private foundation (CTA); Company (GLC); Technology (MST); Research and knowledge, policy transference, stakeholder engagement (IFAPA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acting as a business connector, facilitating connections and collaborations within the ecosystem. Sharing knowledge, information, and experiences related to events, EU regulations, and ongoing projects and initiatives. Disseminating pertinent activities within their sector to enhance awareness and engagement.

SILL number	Organisations involved	Profile	Type of involvement
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Providing valuable inputs on thematic topics for discussion during meetings. • Supporting communication and dissemination efforts to reach out to their network, especially concerning opening calls for enrollment in the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem group.
6	ASINCAR; ALDELIS; EROSKI	Cluster (ASINCAR); Technology (ASINCAR); Company (ALDELIS – food processor; EROSKI - Retailer/supermarket)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acting as a business connector, fostering connections and collaborations within the ecosystem. • Supporting the communication and dissemination of open calls and public activities promoted by the Zero FLW Business Ecosystem group. • Sharing knowledge, information, and experiences related to events, EU regulations, and showcase projects and initiatives. • Disseminating pertinent activities within their sector to enhance awareness and engagement. • Providing valuable inputs on thematic topics for discussion during meetings.
7	WU; TiU	Universities/Research (WU; TiU)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sharing knowledge, information, and experiences related to events, EU regulations, and ongoing projects and initiatives. • Disseminating pertinent activities within their area of research, with a business-oriented perspective. • Supporting dissemination actions to reach out to their network, particularly concerning opening calls for enrollment in the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem group.

SILL number	Organisations involved	Profile	Type of involvement
8	SONAE; University of Minho	Company/Business (SONAE; Allmicroalgae); University (University of Minho)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acting as a business connector, fostering connections and collaborations within the ecosystem. Sharing knowledge, information, and experiences related to events, EU regulations, and ongoing projects and initiatives. Disseminating pertinent activities within their sector to enhance awareness and engagement. Contributing inputs on thematic topics for discussion during meetings.
9	Tilburg University; Wageningen University; Voedingscentrum	Universities (Tilburg University; Wageningen University; Research (Voedingscentrum)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sharing knowledge, information, and experiences related to events, EU regulations, and showcase projects and initiatives. Disseminating pertinent activities within their area of research, with a business-oriented perspective. Supporting communication and dissemination actions to reach out to their network, particularly concerning opening calls for enrollment in the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem group.

3.3 External synergies: Sister Projects

Projects with aligned goals in Food Loss and Waste, particularly those focused on farming, smart technologies, rural economy, and bio-based industries, among others, were identified. These examples served as an initial selection (in collaboration with WP9), as the team planned to broaden the network over the course of the project. Given their direct involvement with FLW, these projects offered valuable access to networks, facilitated information exchange, and could contribute to meetings by presenting opportunities for financing FLW initiatives, among other potential collaborations.

Table 6. Initial list of identified Sister Projects

Initial list of identified Sister Projects
<p>BREADCRUMB is a three-year initiative under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme (2024-2026), funded to investigate the purpose and impact of food marketing standards on food waste (FW) generation. The project aimed to offer evidence-based insights into these standards and their effects, proposing interventions that struck a balance between reducing food waste and achieving other objectives. Ultimately, BREADCRUMB sought to empower food chain actors to maximise the commercial potential of suboptimal food.</p>
<p>CHORIZO, co-funded by the Horizon Europe programme, was dedicated to deepening our understanding of the relationship between social norms, consumer behaviours, economic actor decisions, and food loss and waste (FLW) generation. Leveraging this knowledge, the project aimed to enhance decision-making processes and foster greater engagement among food chain actors, all with the ultimate objective of achieving zero food waste.</p> <p>The project's primary focus was on bridging existing research gaps and utilising its findings to develop and promote innovations that supported more effective engagement in food waste prevention and reduction activities. In essence, CHORIZO was a collaborative European initiative that brought together EU policymakers and food chain actors to enhance collective knowledge and develop new tools to facilitate successful transitions toward minimising FLW. CHORIZO and ZeroW jointly organised their Final Events in Brussels.</p>
<p>The WASTELESS project, which ran from 2023 to 2025, endeavoured to create tools and recommendations for effectively measuring and monitoring food losses and waste (FLW), with the overarching aim of reducing FLW by at least 20% annually. The project's primary objective was to develop measurement tools tailored to critical and lesser-known food supply chains and to propose methodologies for quantifying FLW data. Additionally, WASTELESS pioneered an innovative suite of decision-support tools designed for stakeholders across the EU's food chain, facilitating the long-term reduction and reutilisation of food waste. To achieve its goals, WASTELESS conducted five case studies that examined the utilisation and role of specific food groups, such as fruits and vegetables, fruit juices, processed meat, dairy products, and cereals, in contributing to FLW. Through these endeavours, the project aimed to advance our understanding of FLW dynamics and devised strategies for more efficient FLW management and reduction.</p>
<p>SISTERS project was dedicated to reducing food loss and waste throughout the main stages of the Food Value Chain in Europe. It aimed to achieve this through targeted innovations at each stage of the chain. For instance, the team developed new tools for primary producers to promote direct and Short Chain sales and pioneered technological innovations in packaging for processors and retailers. Additionally, the project included awareness campaigns on food loss and waste, targeting both retailers and consumers.</p>

Sister projects were actively sought for engagement to expand the portfolio, with the goal of involving them not only in dissemination and network outreach but also

in gaining insights into upcoming opportunities relevant to our members. A pivotal role could be played by these sister projects in fostering communication and dissemination synergies, promoting events within the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem group, and establishing strong relationships with programs to relay valuable call opportunities and advantages to our members. Additionally, project representatives were welcomed to share their opportunities during the group's meetings, enriching discussions and fostering collaboration.

The sister projects united in a collaborative endeavour, pooling their expertise and insights to craft a [blog post](#) (Fig 23) on their combined efforts to combat food waste. This joint effort aimed to showcase the diverse array of initiatives undertaken by these projects, offering a comprehensive overview of their shared dedication to addressing this pressing global issue.

Figure 23. Screenshot of blog post from Sisters Project EU website

Looking ahead, joint collaborations with sister projects for future panel discussions were anticipated. When resources and expertise were combined, deep dives into crucial topics like food loss and waste became possible. These discussions weren't just about understanding challenges better; they also generated new ideas and actions. Together, a bigger impact could be made and progress toward shared goals within the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem group could also be accelerated. Additionally, curiosity existed about whether any solutions have been successfully put into practice, with an eagerness to learn from those successes.

3.4 Internal project set-up: AB members

The Advisory Board (AB) members were esteemed stakeholders who played a crucial role in ZeroFLW as observers, providing valuable input, recommendations,

and expertise. Given that some AB members possessed a background in commerce and business, their insights could be particularly beneficial for the Ecosystem.

They could offer recommendations on topics to be discussed, suggest relevant contacts for group integration, and provide guidance on commercial and business-related matters. Participation in these activities was voluntary and aligned with the interests of the advisory board members. The contributions AB members provided to the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem Group included advising on relevant events for group stakeholders, offering to speak or present on relevant subjects during group meetings, suggesting thematic topics with business/commercial relevance, and promoting and disseminating the group within their networks.

3.3 Internal and External Groups and Platforms

Figure 24. Screenshot of ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem closed Group on LinkedIn

Both internal and external platforms were utilised in these efforts. The EU Platform on Food Losses and Waste played a crucial role in mobilizing relevant actors within the EU strategy to reduce food loss and waste, as part of the Farm to Fork Strategy. Although the Platform initially concluded in December 2021, it was re-established in 2022 for a second mandate extending until 2026. The engagement included not only public entities but also the target audience, private sector organizations with business and commercial interests. Additionally, the Platform had a specific subgroup dedicated to food loss and waste (FLW), which could be highly beneficial for involvement in the Ecosystem.

Internal. To complement this, the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem, an internal platform, was established as a closed LinkedIn group. LinkedIn, a well-established channel, facilitated professional networking and collaboration. This approach within the ZeroW project successfully fostered focused communication and collaboration. The closed LinkedIn group provided a secure environment for members to share insights, discuss strategies, and coordinate efforts, thereby enhancing the overall effectiveness of the initiative to reduce food loss and waste.

External. The ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem leveraged the EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub, an external platform that was an official website of the European Union, to promote its initiatives and engage a broader audience. By utilising this hub, the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem effectively communicated its goals and progress, reaching key stakeholders and potential collaborators across Europe. This strategic use of the EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub was instrumental in

raising awareness and fostering participation in the ecosystem's activities. Moving forward, there were plans to continue using this platform to publicise future events and meetings, ensuring sustained visibility and ongoing engagement with the wider community dedicated to reducing food loss and waste.

Figure 25. Screenshot of EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub website

In addition to the EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub, another external platform, the Sustainable Food Systems Network (SFSN), was utilised to promote the recent ZeroW Public Panel Discussion on the Commercialisation of Innovative FLW Technologies. The SFSN, with its extensive membership of over 2,000 individuals, included a diverse array of EU projects and relevant stakeholders committed to sustainable food systems. By promoting the panel discussion on this platform, the initiative successfully engaged a wide and relevant audience, ensuring robust participation and discourse on the commercialisation of FLW technologies. Looking ahead, the Sustainable Food Systems Network was to continue to be a key platform for publicising future events and meetings, maintaining strong connections with stakeholders and fostering ongoing collaboration within the EU food systems community.

 Mirana Khanom
Project Manager – F6S 19 Mar 2024

ZeroW Public Panel Discussion on Commercialisation of Innovative FLW Technologies

Join us for a dynamic panel discussion on R&D to Commercialisation: Challenges and Strategies for Food Loss and Waste Innovative Technologies!

 Date: March 27th
 Time: 11:00 - 12:30 CET

Innovation in tackling food loss and waste is crucial for a sustainable future. Our esteemed panelists will delve into the journey of innovative technologies from research and development to successful commercialisation.

Don't miss this opportunity to gain valuable insights and contribute to the conversation!

 Register now to secure your spot:
<https://lnkd.in/e9AraxdF>

FROM R&D TO COMMERCIALISATION: CHALLENGES AND STRATEGIES FOR FOOD LOSS AND WASTE INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES.

Part of the ZeroW Project Public Panel Discussions

March 27, 2024
11:00 CET

REGISTER NOW!

ZERO Funded by the European Union Grant Agreement no. 101036388

TAKE ACTION WITH US TO COMBAT FOOD LOSS AND WASTE

Figure 26. Screenshot of Panel Discussion posted on Sustainable Food Systems Network (SFSN) Group

3.5 Recruitment Campaign for the Ecosystem Expansion

In (M40) April 2025, F6S launched a recruitment campaign aimed at attracting new members to the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem. The campaign sought to engage a broad range of stakeholders, including innovators, entrepreneurs, investors, policymakers, and organisations working to reduce food loss and waste across the value chain.

Although the campaign did not result in a large influx of new members, it successfully attracted several new participant who shared our commitment to tackling food loss and waste. This addition brought valuable insights and contributed to strengthening the collaborative efforts within the ZeroW project. While the recruitment campaign did not meet the initial expectations in terms of scale, it nonetheless added a significant members to the ecosystem.

Figure 27. Recruitment campaign for the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem on the SFSN platform

Figure 28. Recruitment campaign for the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem on the LinkedIn

The communication content to implement these actions was created by F6S in coordination with the WP10 and WP9 partners to align and present a harmonious language and images associated to the project actions (WP10), as well as to calibrate and better define the target audience (WP9). The campaign for new members, that ran from M19, used social media channels, website and newsletter of the ZeroW project, as well as networks of enrolled stakeholders. All the communication materials were provided by F6S with the collaboration of the WP10 for posting and verification of the message and image.

4 Organisation & Implementation

4.1 ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem Structure

The strategy for engagement and organisation of the **ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem** was a combination of internal and external actions. These actions aimed to engage not only WP Leaders but also SILLs and external stakeholders dedicated to FLW business, in order to achieve the desired number, variety, and quality of stakeholders who contributed to the group's added value and outcomes for its members.

Figure 29 presented the three main levels of actors involved and their level of participation. At the base of the pyramid were the external stakeholders, from which a higher number of participants was expected. This group was specifically composed of individuals with business, commercial, and industrial profiles in the Food Loss and Waste sector.

Task 7.5 Clustering & Commercial Ecosystem Creation Systemic Innovation management & demonstration

Figure 29. Type of participants and level of engagement in the Zero FLW Business Ecosystem

These were the members that we expected to receive inputs from and counted on their active participation in the LinkedIn group, meetings, polls, and forms. This engagement was meant to keep the group active by creating content, promoting networking and exchanging relevant information that led to an enabling environment for commercial links, investments, and business partnerships. Therefore, actions such as meetings with dynamic engagement and discussions of interest, as well as an active search for inputs through Google Forms and an exchange of information on the digital platform of their interest were crucial to keeping external members active and capturing their interest. Partners and SILLs could also contribute to keeping the dynamic alive.

F6S, as the task lead, assumed a crucial role that included reaching out, promoting actions that created content (either through project partners or external stakeholders), organizing initiatives, and engaging ZeroW partners. F6S was the central point of contact and the partner that set the tone for the activities and dynamics that were created between the members of the group.

At the top of the pyramid, we could find the SILLs, partners, and AB members from the project. As part of the project, they were essential in sharing their expertise, experience, and opinions and being part of this co-creation process. The engagement from these actors allowed the group to develop toward the ZeroW goals and attain the members' needs and expectations by, for example, suggesting thematic topics and sharing information, articles, and financing opportunities on the digital platform. Their participation was voluntary, but it was undoubtedly important to the success of the group, as their network and expertise in FLW were determinant for the group's enlargement, initiatives, success, and lifespan.

F6S also held cohort open calls on a regular basis to attract more members to join the group. The regularity of the open calls for expressions of interest depended on the demand of stakeholders per area to integrate the group and on the group's inputs for at least every six months. The enrolments were made through a Google Form, which was linked to the ZeroW Website. The link to the enrolment platform, as well as a description about the group's interests, target profiles, benefits, and goals, was also disseminated through ZeroW's social networks, websites, and newsletter. Synergies between WP7 (Task 7.5) and WP10 supported the dissemination and communication of this initiative.

4.2 ZeroFLW Capacity Building Sessions for Engagement

A **Commercial Partnership Training session** was held online on 22 May 2025 for ZeroW SILL Coordinators and project partners. The session aimed to strengthen participants' understanding of how to identify, approach, and structure strategic commercial partnerships to support the scaling and market uptake of their solutions.

Figure 30. Screenshot of Commercial Partnerships training session for SILLs

The session featured a keynote presentation by Patrícia Almeida, Director at Beta-i, who shared practical guidance on aligning value propositions with industry needs, engaging the right partners, and developing mutually beneficial partnership models. The presentation included examples from the food and sustainability sectors and highlighted lessons learned from cross-sector collaboration.

The session concluded with an interactive Q&A, during which participants discussed specific partnership challenges and explored tailored approaches relevant to their contexts. The final remarks introduced the upcoming SILL Showcase in June 2025, positioning it as a next step in external stakeholder engagement.

As part of the ZeroW capacity-building and business ecosystem engagement activities, an online **SILLs Showcase** was held on 25 June 2025. The session brought together over 60 registered participants from across the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem, including policymakers, researchers, technology providers, end users, and investors.

The Showcase was designed to provide a platform for selected Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) to present their progress, results, and scale-up ambitions to an external audience and receive direct feedback. A total of six SILLs (1, 2, 4, 5, 6, and 8) participated in the event. Each SILL was given five minutes to present, followed by a short Q&A session and a concluding group discussion to explore cross-cutting issues.

Figure 31. Screenshot of ZeroW SILLs Showcase recording

The featured solutions covered a broad spectrum of innovations, including AI-powered classification of non-conforming produce (SILL 5), data platforms for food loss and waste tracking (SILL 1), sustainable smart packaging (SILL 2), process optimisation in poultry production using sensor technologies (SILL 6), modular processing hubs for surplus fruits and vegetables (SILL 4), and circular valorisation of food waste through microalgae production (SILL 8).

The event offered SILL teams the opportunity to:

- Share implementation insights, technical achievements, and pilot outcomes
- Articulate their value proposition and plans for post-project sustainability
- Gather feedback from stakeholders regarding market alignment, data-sharing, and scale-up readiness

Several critical themes emerged during the interactive discussion:

- Data sharing remains a major barrier for FLW monitoring platforms, with trust, incentives, and integration with EU Data Spaces seen as essential enablers.
- Market viability and minimum viable scale were key concerns for technology-intensive models, especially in competitive or saturated sectors.

- Retail readiness and consumer acceptance were discussed in relation to pricing, adoption, and the importance of clearly communicating added value.
- The role of policy frameworks, such as the EU Data Act and circular economy regulations, was highlighted as central to enabling innovation uptake.

The Showcase also underlined the varying levels of commercial maturity among the SILLs, with some at advanced TRL stages (7–8) and preparing for market entry, while others are refining their business models and stakeholder strategies. It also revealed the importance of continued ecosystem engagement, policy alignment, and tailored support for exploitation planning.

Consortium members also attended events (online and offline) to promote the Ecosystem Engagement. Full list of events attended is presented in D10.2. For example, F6S attended the Next Bite: Founders Day 2025 event on 16 June 2025 with the strategic objectives of meeting with investors, promoting the final event, and engaging new stakeholder members.

Figure 32. F6S at EIT Next Bite: Founders Day 2025

The event's focus on connecting entrepreneurs, investors, and corporates within the sustainable food and technology sector provided a highly relevant and targeted platform for our team. We leveraged the high-level networking opportunities to engage directly with potential investors and a wide array of new stakeholders. These discussions were critical for understanding market trends and for forging meaningful connections that could contribute to the ZeroW network's growth. Furthermore, the forum was an excellent event to build excitement for our upcoming final event. Through direct conversations

and collaborative discussions, we were able to raise awareness and invite key industry participants, thereby expanding the reach and potential impact of our project.

4.3 Sustainability of the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem

The ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem has grown into a community of stakeholders from across the agrifood value chain, including innovators, corporates, investors, policymakers, and researchers. To ensure its continuity beyond the lifetime of the ZeroW project, we are committed to keeping the group active and evolving as a platform for collaboration, knowledge-sharing, and scaling opportunities. Post-project, the group will:

- **Serve as a Community Hub** – A dedicated online space where members continue to exchange insights, news, funding opportunities, and lessons learned from piloted solutions.
- **Enable Cross-Project Synergies** – We will integrate the ecosystem into upcoming EU projects, ensuring continuity and positioning it as a ready-made platform to engage with stakeholders.
- **Promote Scaling Opportunities** – Continue to showcase innovations that emerge from ZeroW and other projects, offering a channel for investors and industry to connect with promising solutions.
- **Support Policy & Market Dialogue** – Maintain discussions on systemic innovation, regulatory changes, and market needs to bridge the gap between innovators and decision-makers.

F6S aims to broaden the groups reach, and create long-term impact by embedding the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem into future projects and activities. This approach guarantees that the community built under ZeroW will continue to thrive, scale solutions, and contribute to reducing food loss and waste across Europe and beyond.

5 Summary

The Zero FLW Business Ecosystem group's main goal was to bring together individuals who were interested in turning food waste into a sustainable business. It was this commercial and business focus, directed to external stakeholders involved directly or indirectly in FLW, that was relevant for partners and SILLs in the ZeroW project.

External stakeholders with commercial insight, including investors, corporates, MNEs, venture capitalists, and food banks, brought added value to the discussions and enabled a sound environment to support spin-offs. They also provided a collective learning context by gathering experts in the fields of commerce, industry, and consumer and provider relations within the FLW sector.

Initial goals of creating a group of at least 50 relevant members were achieved and expanded to 100, engaging industry partners, government agencies, nonprofits, and research institutions. By M30, the ecosystem had 117 members, who were actively seeking to enrich the community with expertise in commercialisation, fostering collaboration, innovation, and knowledge exchange. As of M46, the ecosystem had 129 members.

The main goal was to create a context that enabled a connection with the right partners in FLW and created a fertile environment to open opportunities for SILLs and ZeroW partners to engage investors, potential business partners, consumer groups, NGOs, and food banks.

The ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem was proactive in fostering stakeholder engagement through a series of strategic actions. These included the launch of a public Expression of Interest, aimed at drawing interest and participation from a wide audience. Additionally, both internal and public webinars were conducted to provide clarity on the ecosystem's objectives and extend invitations for collaboration. A virtual kick-off event further motivated efforts, setting the stage for dynamic interactions and future endeavours. Subsequent meetings explored topics such as FLW Monitoring and Assessment and efficient food bank networks, offering interactive sessions and expert insights. The ecosystem was positioned to refine its focus, with the thematic specifically geared toward commercialisation. This approach was intended to pinpoint promising collaborations for market penetration, thereby advancing initiatives for economic efficiency and sustainability.

By working through synergies in the project and using all the advantages of the size and expertise of the project partners and SILLs, the team re-enforced the success of this initiative to reach different fields of interest, geographic areas, and diverse stakeholders. This variety complemented the group and added overall value, as using different views, approaches, and profiles could empower the group and allow it to reach a wider landscape of FLW, assessing its state and requirements.

Several projects with similar goals in food loss and waste (FLW) were identified to enhance network outreach and information sharing. BREADCRUMB investigated the impact of food marketing standards on FLW, CHORIZO focused on the interplay between social norms and FLW, WASTELESS developed tools to measure and reduce FLW by at least 20% annually, and SISTERS targeted FLW reduction across the Food Value Chain in Europe. These projects collaborated to promote events, share opportunities during the meetings, and planned joint panel discussions, combining resources and expertise to generate new ideas and accelerate progress toward shared goals within the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem.

Both internal and external platforms were effectively utilised to enhance efforts in reducing food loss and waste. Internally, the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem used a closed LinkedIn group to facilitate professional networking and collaboration. Externally, it leveraged the EU Food Loss and Waste Prevention Hub and the Sustainable Food Systems Network (SFSN) to promote initiatives, engage stakeholders, and publicise events. These platforms ensured sustained visibility, robust participation, and ongoing collaboration within the EU food systems community.

The Zero FLW Business Ecosystem provided the project with a link to external actors, opening up an environment that could provide market opportunities and access to information on consumer, business, and investor needs. Therefore, the implementation of this task, through the Zero FLW Business Ecosystem, was intended to bring benefits to all members involved and to the project overall. With ZeroW as a launching ground and context, the Zero FLW Business Ecosystem was set as a group that was intended to continue to live beyond the project's lifetime.

6 References

Internal documents

- ZeroW Grant Agreement
- ZeroW WP9 tracking sheet
- D7.1 : Market Analyses
- D9.: Action plan for liaison & stakeholder engagement

Digital references

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- <https://copa-cogeca.eu/>
- <https://www.foodrus.eu/cooperation/>

7 Appendix I: List of entities enrolled to the ZeroW Business Ecosystem

	Name of Organisation	Main field/area of work	Country
1	Ingredalia SL	Recovery of functional ingredients from agri-food business by-products // Valorization of food loss	España
2	NGO "Enraiza Derechos"	Food waste	Spain
3	Munster Technological University, Kerry	Sustainable Food Systems	Ireland
4	InQube Innoventures Limited	Farm and Food Tech ERP platform	United Kingdom
5	Redrose Developments Ltd	Macroalgae cultivation and processing	Ireland
6	That's Fresh	Food waste reduction through a mobile app	Serbia
7	University of Copenhagen	Food system transformation through digitalization	Denmark
8	Permapot	Urban gardening/farming	Germany
9	Foodways Consulting GmbH	Supply Chain / Hospitality & Food Service	Switzerland
10	Phenix	Marketing & Communication Manager	España
11	Hygia Consult	management	România
12	Justus-Liebig University, Giessen	Food Loss and Waste Research in Nigeria	Germany
13	Feeding Albania Foundation	Food Banking and FLW Systems in Albania	Albania
14	Foodscale Hub	EU-funded projects, mostly H2020 and Horizon Europe	Serbia
15	Oscillum	FoodTech, Food Waste, Food Safety, Agri-food	Spain
16	Hortee	Circular Economy, Digital Platform	Portugal
17	Safe Food Advocacy Europe	Food Safety, FLW reduction, food donations	Belgium
18	OLIO	Impact / Food waste	United Kingdom
19	EcoViridis Environmental Technology	Sustainable Waste Management/Circular Economy	Nigeria
20	SITES	Sustainability	Ireland
21	UWE Bristol	Research	United Kingdom

22	InoSens Doo Novi Sad	Agri tech, Horizon project	Serbia
23	FOODSHARE CLUB LIMITED UK 14023669	Food resque company	The UK
24	Multiscan Technologies SL	Innovation & new technologies	Spain
25	Stonnavation	Sustainable Healthcare	Scotland
26	CETENMA	R&D environment and energy	España
27	GALANAKIS LABORATORIES L.P.	food waste recovery, COVID-19 food systems, greendeal, bioeconomy, food technology, sustainable food	Ελλάδα
28	Self employed	Sustainability Consulting	United Kingdom
29	Harvey Nichols/Brunel University	CSR	United Kingdom
30	CSCP - Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production gGmbH	food waste, food, sustainable lifestyles	Germany
31	ACCIÓN CONTRA EL HAMBRE (ACTION AGAINST HUNGER)	Socio-labour inclusion and food insecurity	España
32	Intelisos Ltd	Circular Economy	United Kingdom
33	Agrifood Partnership of Western Greece	Precision Agriculture	Ελλάδα
34	Výzkumný ústav potravinářský Praha v. v. i.	food engineering	Czech Republic
35	Samen Tegen Voedselverspilling (foudation Food Waste Free United)	Reduction of food loss and waste	the Netherlands
36	2piNET	Agro-Food	Spain
37	Elea Technology GmbH	Pulsed Electric Field Technology	Deutschland
38	FoodWIN	food waste	Belgium
39	Universidad de Burgos	European projects	Spain
40	AINIA	Leader EU Projects	España
41	Fondazione Banco Alimentare ONLUS	Secretariat General area	Italia
42	KU Leuven	Agricultural Economics	Belgium
43	Unión de Pequeños Agricultores y Ganaderos	Farming	España

44	Farrelly & Mitchell	Agri-food/ Consulting	Ireland
45	Kantar	Sustainable Innovation (FMCG)	United Kingdom
46	NONAGON	Technology transfer; IT	Portugal
47	DIH DATAlife	Digitalization	Spain
48	Paradigm-Shifts Design & Communication and o2 Global Network for Sustainable Design	Design and research (bioregional food and fiber systems)	Switzerland
49	AINIA	Product Quality and Preservation	España
50	FAO	sociology/behavior	Hungary
51	The Waste Transformers	Food waste to value on site	Netherlands
52	CLUSTER FEMAC	Agricultural production means	España
53	Oost NL	Business Development Food	Netherlands
54	Petrova Services	Finance	United Kingdom
55	LightBlue Consulting	Food Waste Prevention	Thailand
56	REGION OF WESTERN GREECE	AGRI ENVIRONMENT PROJECTS	GREECE
57	Fraunhofer ISI	Foresight	Germany
58	FoodWIN	Food Waste prevention	België
59	Ghent University	Business Developer End-of-Waste	Belgium
60	Food4Sustainability	By-product management and valorisation	Portugal
61	InQube Innoventures Limited	Farm Value Chain Digitization for optimization, loss reduction and traceability	United Kingdom
62	Johanne Birn	Sustainability, green transition and food waste reduction	Denmark
63	DIH Agrifood Croatia	Food and technology	Croatia
64	University of Greenwich	Food systems research	United Kingdom
65	Department Of Electrical and Computer, Aarhus University	Production and operations management, logistics in the food chain	Danmark
66	REDINN	European projects	Italia
67	FoodAllios	Food Waste	Greece
68	Cooperativas Agro-alimentarias de Andalucía	I+D+i	Spain
69	Vialog	media services	UK
70	Institute of Agricultural and Urban Ecological	Nutrition / Food Science	Germany

	Projects at the Humboldt University Berlin (IASP)		
71	Verein zur Förderung agrar- und stadökologischer Projekte e.V. (A.S.P.)	Scientific Assistant	Germany
72	Mediterranean Food Trade	Business development on international markets for Mediterranean food	Greece
73	Zero Waste Europe	Waste reduction at the local level / circular economy	Belgium
74	Pebble wave	Conscious Purpose Business	België
75	Delhaize	Retail	Belgium
76	bgu university	MBA	israel
77	Ryp Labs	Agtech/biotech	USA and Belgium
78	Hungarian Food Bank Association	food surplus redistribution	Hungary
79	Corporate Finance Advisor (Freelance)	Finance / Investment	United Kingdom
80	AGPHARM BIOINNOVATIONS LLP	Sustainable technologies for enhancing food production, conservation and long term storage. Overarching mission is to enhance global food security and reduce the carbon footprint associated with food loss and wastage	India
81	IMPERFECTUSBOX, SL	No fruits and vegetables waste	Spain
82	RSK ADAS Ltd.	Food and agriculture sustainability (consulting)	Belgium/ UK
83	Affabelle CIC	Retail	Uk
84	TALKUAL	ECOMMERCE	SPAIN
85	University of Santiago de Compostela	Analytical Chemistry, bioactives recovery from agri-food wastes	Spain
86	GAIA EPICHEIREIN SA	EU R&I Projects on the digital transformation of the agrifood sector	Greece
87	SINTEF Ocean	Research	Norway
88	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL	Project manager of Research & Innovation Projects	Greece
89	Sustainable Innovations	Business Consulting and Services	Spain
90	Teagasc	Agriculture, food and bioeconomy	Ireland
91	SINTEF Ocean	FLW, Life cycle assessment, food systems	Norway
92	Q-PLAN INTERNATIONAL ADVISORS PC	Economist / EU Project Manager	Greece

93	COMET GLObal Innovation	research	Spain
94	STRATAGEM ENERGY LTD	COMMUNICATION-DISSEMINATION-EXPLOITATION CONSULTANTS	CYPRUS
95	Stratagem LTD	Research & Innovation	Cyprus
96	Newcastle University	Marketing, rural enterprise	UK
97	Caserio Consulente	Sustainable development	United Kingdom
98	Belit Ltd.	IT	Serbia
99	EuroCommerce	Retail and Wholesale	Belgium
100	Academy of Scientific Research and Technology	STI policy	Egypt
101	Municipality of Halandri Athens, Greece	Chemical Engineering	Greece
102	IFWC	food waste in HaFS	France
103	Boroume	Food Waste	Greece
104	ACR+	Sustainable Food Systems	Belgium
105	European Food Information Council	Food and Health	Belgium
106	MIO-ECSDE	Project officer	Greece
107	BETA TC (UVic - UCC)	Food Loss	Spain
108	Urbaser	Waste management/ Innovation Department	Spain
109	Departament d'Acció Climàtica, Alimentació i Agenda Rural	Food Losses and Food Waste	Spain
110	ISEKI-Food Association	Project management	Austria
111	AITIIP Centro Tecnológico	Head of packaging. Coordination of projects	Spain
112	AMANOS Machinery & Engineering	Process Development/Manufacturing	Türkiye
113	FoodFix	Supply Chain	Israel
114	Food Systems Foresight	Food Systems Advisory Services	Global
115	Ingredalia SL	Upcycled Ingredients	Spain
116	Massachusetts Institute of Technology	food science and engineering/food waste, food safety, food security	USA
117	Private	Technology	Israel
118	Trotec NV	Circulaire food to feed transformation - Project and Innovation	Belgium
119	Trotec NV	Circular economy food to feed transformation - operational manager	Belgium

120	Societe Generale GSC	Business Performance	India
121	smartSense consulting solutions	IT	India
122	Association European Food Systems	Food Systems Transformation	Bosnia & Herzegovina
123	Freelance, Consultant - Circular Economy	Microbiology Society UK, Champion (Advocate)	Philippines
124	OM Solutions	Entrepreneur	Israel
125	Al-Balqa Applied University	Education	Jordan
126	Copenhagen Business School	Sustainable consumer behaviour	Denmark
127	Biblical Foods Ltd	Food Production	United Kingdom
128	Opolo Global Innovation	Food system sustainability	Nigeria
129	Ozyegin University	Operations Management	Turkiye

8 Appendix II: Internal and External Questionnaires Results

Questionnaires were shared during the Internal and Public webinars organised in November 2022. Analysis of 48 gathered answers is presented down below.

Internal Questionnaire Results

What kind of FLW stakeholders are more relevant to engage in a commercial/business community linked to the ZeroW project?

The aim was to narrow down the list of stakeholders to 4 main ones, that would subsequently become the focus for future user engagement. Project partners enlisted **industry players, big retailers, scale-ups and farmers** as the most relevant stakeholders for the project currently.

What do you think are the priority thematic that the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem should focus on during the monthly meetings?

The aim was to narrow down the topics to 4 main ones, that would subsequently become the focus of future group meetings. Project partners chose **Supply Chain Challenges** as the most relevant topic for the project currently, followed by **Technological and Digital Solutions** for zero food loss and waste domain, as well as **smart specialisation** in agri-food domain.

What involvement would you be willing to have with the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem? (You can choose several options): [Ways to engage and be active]

The aim was to discover the preferred ways of entities to be engaged in the Ecosystem. Project partners mentioned that **participating in meetings** is the preferred way to active, accompanied by giving recommendations of stakeholders to integrate the group, and sharing FLW news and information of interest in the digital platform.

Please specify how often you think the Zero FLW Business Ecosystem meetings should take place.

The aim was to set the occurrence of the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem Meetings. Project partners stated that meetings should happen **once every two months**.

External Questionnaire Results

What kind of FLW stakeholders are more relevant to engage in a commercial/business community linked to the ZeroW project?

The aim was to narrow down the list of stakeholders to 4 main ones, according to external stakeholders. **Big retailers, industry, farmers and start-ups** are enlisted as the most relevant stakeholders for the project currently.

What do you think are the priority thematic that the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem should focus on during the monthly meetings?

The aim was to narrow down the topics to 4 main ones, that would subsequently become the focus of future group meetings. External stakeholders chose **Supply Chain Challenges** as the most relevant topic for the project currently, followed by **harvesting and post-harvesting**, and **smart specialisation** in agri-food domain.

What involvement would you be willing to have with the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem? (You can choose several options): [Ways to engage and be active]

The aim was to discover the preferred ways of external entities to be engaged in the Ecosystem. **Participating in meetings** is the preferred way to active, accompanied by **being a speaker** on a certain topic, and **sharing FLW news** and information of interest in the digital platform.

Please specify how often you think the Zero FLW Business Ecosystem meetings should take place.

The aim was to set the occurrence of the ZeroFLW Business Ecosystem Meetings. External stakeholders stated that meetings should happen **once every two months**.

